

Pathogenicity of *Beauveria bassiana* on brown planthopper (BPH), whitebacked planthopper (WBPH), and green leafhopper (GLH)

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B. bassiana is an entomogenous fungus important in microbial insect control. Several strains isolated from BPH, GLH, and WBPH in Asia were bioassayed to determine their virulence on planthoppers and leafhoppers in the laboratory.

Spores of each isolate, at 10¹⁴/ha, were suspended in sterile distilled water + 0.5% Tween 80 surfactant. Thirty-d-old rice plants were sprayed with the spore suspension at 2 ml/pot, based on a 300-litre spray volume/ha, and 20 insects/pot were placed in mylar tube cages. Dead insects were removed daily for 7 d and allowed to incubate for 1 d before microscope examination for infection.

Isolates E, RS149, and 101481-5 were the most virulent against all insect species (Table 1). RS149 and 101481-5 had higher virulence to BPH than to GLH and WBPH. BPH was most susceptible to *B. bassiana*. Isolates RS413, 102381-8C, and E had higher virulence to BPH and GLH than to WBPH.

In another test, isolates 102381-8C, GLH-8, and GLH-20 were the most virulent to BPH (Table 2). The other isolates except GLH-1 had moderate virulence. Isolates 102381-8C, GLH-4, and GLH-5 were most virulent against GLH. GLH-20 was more pathogenic to BPH

Table 1. Pathogenicity and comparative virulence of different *B. bassiana* isolates to BPH, GLH, and WBPH in the laboratory, IRRI, 1983.

Isolate (I) ^a	Infection ^b (%)			
	BPH	GLH	WBPH	I-means
RS149	53 a (a)	34 a (b)	16 a (c)	34 ab
RS413	36 abc (a)	35 a (a)	16 a (b)	29 b
RS252	30 bc (a)	29 a (a)	29 a (a)	29 b
102081-2	31 abc (a)	28 a (a)	18 a (a)	25 b
101481-5	49 ab (a)	29 a (b)	23 a (b)	33 ab
102381-8C	33 abc (a)	29 a (ab)	18 a (b)	26 b
E	50 ab (a)	41 a (ab)	26 a (b)	39 a
Untreated	0 d	0 b	0 b	0 c
T-means	35 (a)	28 (b)	18 (b)	

^aRS149 = French strain; RS252, RS413 and BTI Bb = US. strains; 102081-2, 102381-8C, and E from BPH in China; 101481-5 from GLH in China. ^bIn a column and in a row (in parentheses), means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by DMRT.

Table 2. Pathogenicity and comparative virulence of different *B. bassiana* isolates to BPH, GLH, and WBPH in the laboratory, IRRI, 1983.

Isolate (I) ^a	Infection ^b (%)			
	BPH	GLH	WBPH	I-means
GLH-1	14 c (a)	14 c (a)	24 a (ab)	17 c
GLH-3	30 abc (a)	14 c (a)	15 a (a)	20 bc
GLH-4	25 abc (ab)	40 ab (a)	11a (b)	25 bc
GLH-5	20 bc (a)	28 abc (a)	24 a (a)	24 bc
GLH-6	25 abc (a)	13 c (a)	23 a (a)	20 bc
GLH-8	43 ab (a)	20 bc (a)	33 a (a)	32 ab
GLH-9	34 abc (a)	19 c (a)	26 a (a)	26 bc
GLH-11	24 abc (a)	18 bc (a)	16 a (a)	19 bc
GLH-16	39 abc (a)	18 c (b)	25 a (ab)	27 bc
GLH-22	24 abc (a)	11 c (a)	18 a (a)	18 c
GLH-19	31 abc (a)	16 c (a)	25 a (a)	24 bc
GLH-20	51 a	11 c (b)	25 a (b)	29 abc
102081-2	29 abc (a)	24 bc (a)	19 a (a)	24 bc
102381-8C	46 ab (a)	53 a (a)	29 a (a)	43 a
Untreated	0 d	0 d	0 b	0 d
T-means	29 (a)	21 (ab)	20 (ab)	23

^aGLH 1-20 collected from the Philippines; 102081-2 and 102381-8C collected from BPH in China. ^bIn a column and in a row (in parentheses), means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by DMRT.

than to GLH and WBPH, and isolate GLH-4 was more virulent to GLH and BPH than to WBPH. The results suggest

that *B. bassiana* strains have potential as microbial agents to control BPH, GLH, and WBPH. □

Leafroller (LF) outbreak in Haryana, India

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Before 1982 LF *Cnaphalocrocis medinalis* Guenée (Lepidoptera: Pyralidae) was a minor pest in Haryana, averaging 5-12%

infestation. In 1983 kharif, infestation caused 60-70% leaf damage. Infestation began the first week of Aug and continued to mid-Oct, probably encouraged by heavy rainfall in late Jul (197.9 mm) and Aug (264.1 mm). An average 20% damage was observed in Ambala, 27% in Karnal, 29% in Sirsa, and 31% in Kurukshetra. Populations were higher on the late transplanted crop. There were no differences in damage between scented and unscented varieties. □

***Cryptoblabes gnidiella*, a fern-feeding caterpillar, and its parasites**

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In 1983 wet season, *Cryptoblabes gnidiella* (Millière) were feeding and breeding on azolla in and around the Mandya Rice Research Station. The semi-

Parasitization of azolla caterpillar, Mandya, India.

Sep 1983	Parasitization (%)		
	<i>Apanteles</i> sp.	<i>B. excarinata</i>	<i>Xanthopimpla</i> sp.
Wk1	30	8	1
Wk2	35	9	1
Wk3	43	11	0
Wk4	50	14	4
Mean	40	10	1

aquatic larva forms a tubular structure by folding the azolla and feeds on azolla fronds.

Infestation was slight in Jul, but by Sep 40-45% of the azolla was infested with the caterpillars.

Well-developed larvae and pupae were collected in the field at weekly intervals to identify natural enemies. Larval parasitization by *Apanteles* sp.

(Braconidae) ranged from 30 to 50% with a mean monthly 40% (see table).

The pupal parasite *Brachymeria excarinata* Gahan (Chalcididae) affected 8 to 14% (av 10%) of the caterpillars. *Xanthopimpla* sp. (Ichneumonidae) parasitism was about 1%.

Caterpillar population declined after Sep because large snail populations killed the azolla. □

Wet season population fluctuation of whitebacked planthopper (WBPH) in West Java

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WBPH *Sogatella furcifera* Horvath is a serious rice pest in Karawang, where Cisadane is the most popular variety. We recorded WBPH population fluctuations in 1983-84 wet season in Tunggakjati.

Biweekly sampling was by sweep net, 25 strokes with 10 replications. Captured insects were observed under a binocular microscope and WBPH and its spider predators were counted. At early growth stages, WBPH population was low and less than the spider population. WBPH population peaked 62 d after transplanting, then decreased. The spider population followed a similar trend (see figure).

WBPH and spiders /25 strokes

Number of WBPH and spiders at different ages of Cisadane rice in 1983-84 wet season. Karawang, West Java, Indonesia.

Parasite complex of yellow stem borer (YSB)

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We studied the parasite complex of YSB *Scirpophaga incertulas* (Walk.) from May 1980 to Jun 1982 at TNAU Coimbatore.

Egg and larval YSB parasites at TNAU Coimbatore, India.

Parasite	Family	Host stage affected	Mean parasitism (%)	Month of activity
<i>Tetrastichus schoenobii</i> Ferriere	Eulophidae	Egg	47	Dec-Jan
<i>Telenomus rowani</i> Gahan	Scelionidae	Egg	6	Oct
<i>Telenomus</i> sp.	Scelionidae	Egg	1	Jan-Feb
<i>Scelio</i> sp.	Scelionidae	Egg	1	Jan-Feb
<i>Exoryza schoenobii</i> Wilkinson	Braconidae	Larva	10	Jan-Feb
<i>Rhaconotus</i> sp.	Braconidae	Larva	3	Jan-Feb
<i>Amauromorpha</i> <i>accepta methathoracica</i>	Ichneumonidae	Larva	1	Sep

Four egg and four larval parasites were observed (see table). Egg parasitization was greater (47%) than larval parasitization (10%).

Tetrastichus schoenobii (Ferriere) was the predominant egg parasite. It peaked with 47% parasitism in Dec-Jan. *Apanteles schoenobii* (Wilk) was the predominant larval parasite. □

Pest control and management

WEEDS

Effect of time of herbicide application on rices of different durations

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We studied in 1983 the selectivity and effectiveness of four preemergence

herbicides in a lowland nursery at TNAU. Soil was a clay loam.

Short-duration IR50 (105 d), medium-duration Co 43 (135 d), and long-duration Ponmani (165 d) were the main plot treatments. Herbicides – 1 kg butachlor/ha, 1 kg thiobencarb/ha, 0.5 kg oxadiazon/ha, and 1 kg pendimethalin/ha – were applied at 5 and 8 d after sowing and compared to an untreated control. The field was puddled and pre-